

Interaction of quercetin with DPPC model membrane : Molecular dynamic simulation, DSC and multinuclear NMR studies[†]

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Abstract : Interaction between a drug and model membranes may be crucial for understanding the pharmacological activity. Quercetin (3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavone) possesses anti-inflammatory, anti-neoplastic and cardio-protective activity. In addition, it is a potent antioxidant and is known to act through cell membrane.

The interaction of flavonoids with model membranes using various physical techniques is well documented. In this paper we report, the mode of interaction of quercetin with lipid bilayers prepared from dipalmitoyl phosphatidyl choline (DPPC). The techniques used are molecular dynamic (MD) simulations, 2D NMR and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The MD have been carried out in duplicate for 0.5 ns, 1.2 ns, 5 ns, 10 ns and 20 ns where quercetin shows the propensity of forming H-bonds with the acyl group in the polar head region of the lipid bilayer. The 2D NOESY experiments show the interaction of the 6'H, 5'H, 6H and 8H protons of quercetin with polar head group protons of the lipid bilayer. The findings are further supported by the DSC, ³¹P and ¹³C NMR studies.

Keywords : Quercetin, molecular dynamic simulations, DPPC, NMR, DSC.

Introduction

Flavonoids constitute the most abundant phenolic compounds in plants. Their physiological potentials have attracted much attention in relation to their role in the cellular and extracellular antioxidant defense against oxygen radicals¹⁻³. Recently, there has been a growing interest in flavonoids, especially quercetin, due to its potential beneficial properties in human health.

Quercetin (3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavone) (Fig. 1) is one of the most abundant bioflavonoids present in most edible fruits and vegetables⁴. It consists of two aromatic rings A and B linked by an oxygen-containing heterocyclic ring C. With its potent antioxidant and metal ion chelating capacity, quercetin has been used for the treatment of inflammation, arteriosclerosis, bleeding, allergy and swellings^{5,6}. Additionally, it is among the group of phytoestrogens suggested to reduce the risks of certain cancers^{7,8}. It is considered to be one of the most potent flavonoid which is capable of interacting with and modulat-

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of quercetin

ing activity of a variety of enzyme systems including cyclooxygenase, lipooxygenase, phosphodiesterase and tyrosine kinase. A complete understanding of the mode of action of quercetin, however requires studies of its interaction with possible biological targets such as membranes, nucleic acids, enzymes and proteins⁹.

Lipid membranes are recognized as important media-

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tors in a number of metabolic pathways¹⁰ where phosphatidylcholine plays a key role¹¹. Changes in membrane architecture and endothermic properties can affect multiple biological events that occur at the cellular membrane level^{12,13}. It is therefore important to understand the molecular mechanism of interaction of flavonoids with bio-membranes, which has been a subject of numerous studies¹⁴. Studies are often carried out with model membranes because their composition can be controlled and they can be made to mimic the biomembrane^{15,16}.

Quercetin poses major bioavailability problems. It is present as glycosides in the natural form. The glycosides are too polar, to penetrate the intestinal membranes and hence not very easily absorbed. The release of the aglycone by the action of the microfloral enzymes is needed for the compound to become absorbable. Although the aglycones are permeable, the bioavailability is not very high due to poor solubility and a greater extent of conjugation. Thus, there are multiple challenges associated with the bioavailability of quercetin^{17,18}. These include solubility, permeation and metabolism which together act to reduce the bioavailability of quercetin.

To understand the mode of interaction of quercetin with model membrane we have used biophysical properties of DPPC bilayers using molecular dynamic simulations (MD), DSC and NMR (³¹P, ¹H, ¹³C, and NOESY) techniques.

Materials and methods :

Quercetin and DPPC were purchased from Sigma Chemicals Co., USA. The reagents used were of A.R. grade. NMR experiments were recorded on a BRUKER AVANCE 500 MHz spectrometer. 2D-NOESY (Nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy), spectrum was recorded using standard pulse programs¹⁹. The ³¹P and ¹³C NMR experiments were carried out using a relaxation delay of 1 s using broadband proton decoupling. The data was processed using Topspin 2.0. DSC measurements were performed using a differential scanning calorimeter VP-DSC (Microcal, Northampton, MA, USA). The samples were degassed under vacuum before being loaded into the reference and sample cells. A scan rate of 1.5°C/min over the temperature range 20–60°C was employed. Repeated scans for the same samples were generally superimposable. Data were analyzed with the software ORIGIN provided by Microcal.

Multilamellar vesicles were prepared using standard procedure²⁰. Samples for NMR and DSC were prepared by first dissolving the desired quantity of DPPC in chloroform along with the drug in methanol. The solvent was evaporated with a stream of nitrogen so as to deposit a lipid film on the walls of the container. Last traces of solvent were removed by vacuum drying for at least 1 h. The film was hydrated with the required amount of D₂O at pH 7.2, which was followed by incubation in water bath at 50°C with repeated vortexing. The lipid concentration for NMR samples was maintained at 100 mM while the drug concentration was varied from 10 to 50 mM. For DSC, samples were prepared at various lipid to drug molar ratios starting from 1 : 20 to 1 : 2. Unilamellar vesicles for NMR experiments were prepared by sonicating the above dispersions with a Branson Sonicator-450 at 50% duty cycles till optical clarity was obtained.

Drug-MLV binding constants were determined by the centrifugation method²¹. A fixed drug concentration of 100 μM (in 5% MeOH + 95% H₂O) giving rise a drug : lipid ratio 1 : 2.5 to 1 : 20, was added systematically to varied concentration of lipid MLV's (prepared as described earlier) in the range of 0.25 mg/ml to 2 mg/ml and incubated for 2 h. After incubation it was centrifuged for 0.5 h at 30,000 rpm. The supernatant was taken and its optical density was measured.

The drug concentration in the supernatant was determined by measuring the optical density of the solution and the amount of drug bound to liposomes was determined from the difference. Methanol has a threshold concentration (5.5%) below which it does not affect the binding²². The drug-liposome apparent binding constant (*k*) was analyzed using the double reciprocal plot of 1/(fraction bound) versus 1/(lipid concentration) which yields a straight line with a slope 1/*k*.

Computational studies

Computational studies were carried out using Desmond 2.2 running on CentOS 5.4 Linux workstation. The force field employed for the molecular dynamic simulation was OPLS. The typical system consisted of 24 DPPC molecules and 723 water molecules within the initial dimensions of *x* = 11.6 Å, *y* = 12.3 Å and *z* = 23.2 Å. The simulations were carried out in NPT ensemble and the temperature and the pressure parameters were set to 323

K and 1.01325 bar respectively which are commonly applied conditions for the study of DPPC bilayers. The system was coupled to a Berendsen Thermostat and Barostat. Periodic boundary conditions were enforced. The non-bonded cut-off was set to 9 Å. All the bond lengths involving hydrogen were constrained with SHAKE algorithm.

The simulated system was constructed by inserting quercetin molecule into the middle of the bilayer where there is a relatively large free volume available and therefore the insert position results in least perturbation. The net charge on the system was adjusted to zero. To start the simulation, the system was energy minimized with gradually decreasing harmonic restraints followed by a 0.5 ns relaxation to remove bad contacts by initial relaxation of the lipid and the solvent molecules followed by relaxation of the drug-lipid complex. This was followed by a 10 ns and 20 ns MD simulation. The trajectories were recorded each 4.8 ps.

Results and discussion

(a) Molecular dynamic simulations :

The simulation results indicate the movement of the quercetin molecule from the centre of the bilayer towards the polar head region. This is shown in the snapshot taken at 20 ns (Fig. 2). During entire simulation time, quercetin did not show entry into the core of the bilayer. The trajectory analysis shows that the drug starts moving towards the polar head group region in less than 0.5 ns. During this movement, it forms H-bonds with the acyl groups in the polar region. In the initial stages, as the molecule travels in DPPC bilayers, the H-bonds are being formed and broken. Sometimes as the molecule moves, the number of H-bonds changes from 1 to 2 or from 3 to 4. Also during the motion of the molecule at some point of time, there are no H-bonds. The graph of H-bond formation as a function of time is depicted in Fig. 3. Although the major part of the interaction of quercetin with lipid bilayer involves H-bonding, the hydrophobic part of the molecule i.e. the aromatic rings A and B are orientated towards the hydrophobic core of the lipid bilayer.

The solubility of quercetin is the rate limiting factor in the absorption of the drug²³. Therefore, attempts to improve water-solubility is one of the major approaches in the structural modifications of quercetin. However,

Fig. 2. A snapshot of 20 ns MD simulations of quercetin-DPPC system. Quercetin is shown as yellow colored ring. Nitrogen atoms of polar head region of lipid are shown in blue, oxygens are in red and alkyl chains of DPPC in white. Representative H-bonds are indicated by yellow dotted line.

the water soluble derivatives of quercetin²⁴ also do not show bioavailability of more than 20% indicating that there are other factors responsible for reduced bioavailability. One of the factors required is crossing over the lipid bilayers which involves passage of the drug across the hydrophilic as well as the hydrophobic region. Formation of H-bonds at the polar head region provides an energy barrier which has to be overcome by quercetin in order to enter the hydrophobic core. During the entire 20 ns of simulation time, it is observed that the drug remains associated with the polar head group region and is not able to overcome the H-bonding barrier to enter the hydrophobic core of the lipid bilayer suggesting a rate limiting factor in the absorption of quercetin.

(b) Binding studies with MLVs :

The binding of quercetin with lipid bilayers is shown

Fig. 3. Hydrogen bond formation as a function of time. X-axis shows the time (ns) during which the entire simulations were carried out. Y-axis shows no. of H-bonds observed between quercetin and DPPC at given point of time.

in Fig. 4. It is observed that nearly 70% of the total drug is bound to the lipid bilayers even at relatively low concentration (0.25 mM) of lipid. A plot of the inverse of the fraction of drug bound versus the inverse of the lipid concentration is linear. The apparent binding constant measured for quercetin is 10710 M^{-1} .

tropic behavior, architecture of the lipid bilayer and intermolecular interactions at molecular level.

(c) DSC studies :

Differential scanning calorimetry has proved to be a sensitive technique for studying the effect of the drug on the packing order of the lipid bilayers. The thermotropic

Fig. 4. Binding of quercetin to DPPC MLV's in MeOH (5%)/H₂O (95%) mixture.

In the following sections we address issues concerning the nature of such binding with regard to the thermo-

aspect of drug-lipid interactions can be studied by examining the changes in the melting point (T_m) and the shape

of the DSC trace²⁵.

During heating, the lipid initially undergoes a pre-transition ($L_{\beta'} - P_{\beta'}$) from an ordered 'gel' state where the lipids are ordered and tilted ($L_{\beta'}$) to the $P_{\beta'}$ state where the lipids are still ordered and in a gel state but with a minimal tilt. The pre-transition occurs before the main transition and is small compared to the main one. During the main transition ($P_{\beta'} - L_{\alpha'}$) lipids undergo a change from the ordered state ($P_{\beta'}$) to a fluid disordered state $L_{\alpha'}$ ²⁶.

Quercetin affects the thermotropic behaviour of DPPC multilamellar vesicles, causing change in melting temperature (T_m) typical for DPPC bilayers. It is well known that the interactions between flavonoids and DPPC bilayers leads to the fluidifying effect due to the introduction of lipophilic molecules into the ordered structure of the lipid bilayers²⁷. In fact, drug molecules act as a spacer in such a structure leading to a decrease in the T_m of the gel to liquid crystal phase transition.

Fig. 5 shows the DSC curves of DPPC incorporated with varying concentrations of quercetin. It is observed that the multilamellar structure of plain DPPC shows a

polar head group of DPPC. The mobility of the alkyl chain is seen in the main transition at 41.8°C. The broad pre-transition appears at quercetin : lipid molar ratios 1 : 20, suggesting interaction of DPPC with polar head group leading to changes in the gel $L_{\beta'}$ phase. At higher molar ratios (1 : 10 to 1 : 5) the pre-transition peak disappears and the main transition (T_m) shifts to lower temperatures. At still higher molar ratios (1 : 3-1 : 2) it again shows an increase in T_m value which is consistent with earlier reports²⁸. This behavior leads us to make some considerations concerning the drug distribution into model membranes.

It is known that at high concentrations, drug molecules are less soluble in the rigid structure of the gel phase so that they can aggregate²⁹. The result of such a process is the exclusion of drug molecules from the homogeneous lipid-drug dispersion, causing an increase in T_m .

In addition, the increase in T_m might be due to the tendency of the drug molecules to leave the lipid bilayer to the aqueous medium with time. However, no change in the T_m was observed even when the sample was scanned

Fig. 5. DSC plots of DPPC (50 mM) incorporated with quercetin. The quercetin : lipid molar ratios are (a) 0 : 100, (b) 1 : 20, (c) 1 : 10, (d) 1 : 6.6, (e) 1 : 5, (f) 1 : 3, (g) 1 : 2.5, (h) 1 : 2.

pre-transition or low enthalpy transition at 34°C which is an indication of the mobility of the choline part of the

after 24 h under identical conditions. Therefore, it can be suggested that at lower concentrations, quercetin is firmly

bound to the DPPC and with increase in concentration, it aggregates.

(d) *NMR experiments* :

¹³C NMR : To probe deeper into the nature of the interaction between quercetin and the lipid membrane, ¹³C NMR experiments have been carried out for quercetin alone and in the presence of the lipid bilayers (spectra not shown). The assignments for ¹³C NMR spectra of quercetin have been made using the DEPT spectrum³⁰ and from the multiplicity pattern of the resonances. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of the DPPC bilayers has been assigned as reported in the literature³¹.

The spectra of the DPPC bilayers and quercetin show that most of the drug signals are broadened (as compared to the pure form), with the exception of a few signals which remain sharp (spectra not shown). The broadening of the signals arises due to an exchange at an intermediate time scale between the bound and free form. Due to the broadening of the signals it was difficult to measure the spin lattice relaxation (T_1) and the spin-spin relaxation times (T_2), which are measures of the overall tum-

bling and segmental motions in the molecule. In the fast tumbling range, both T_1 and T_2 are large, typically of the order of 10 s³². The estimates of spin-spin relaxation times (T_2) from the NMR line-width indicate that the T_2 values are of the order of 100 ms. Lower values of T_2 indicate that the molecules lose their mobility and become strongly bound to lipid bilayers resulting in a loss of motional freedom. This also indicates an increase in the motional ordering of the lipid acyl chain and head group. However a few signals which remain relatively sharp indicate the mobility of the respective atoms. The results indicate a strong binding of quercetin with DPPC.

(e) *2D NOESY* : The 2D NOESY contains a wealth of information on intermolecular interactions as well as the conformation (from intra-molecular NOE's) of the molecules in the lipid bilayer. These NOE's arise when the two atoms (within the molecule or from two different molecules) are at a distance ≤ 5 Å apart.

The NOESY spectrum of quercetin incorporated into DPPC unilamellar vesicles is shown in Fig. 6. The assignments for quercetin and lipid peaks which show in-

Fig. 6. 500 MHz 2D ¹H NOESY spectrum of DPPC unilamellar vesicles incorporated with quercetin (1 : 5 drug : lipid molar ratio). The experiment was carried out at 323 K with a mixing time of 400 ms.

termolecular NOE's are indicated in the figure along the F2 and F1 dimensions respectively. The intermolecular NOE's seen between the lipid and quercetin, show a number of additional NOE's as compared to the NOESY spectrum of quercetin or lipid alone. The additional interactions involve both the polar head and the acyl chain of the lipid.

The 5'H, 6'H, 6H and 8H protons show NOEs and thereby interactions with polar head group (-N(CH₃)₃). In addition 6H and 8H protons show NOEs with (CH₂)_n of the alkyl chain as well. It may be further noted that these two protons (6H and 8H) shift to downfield by 0.2 and 0.4 ppm, respectively indicating their hydrophobic interactions with the alkyl chain of the lipid bilayer.

These experimental results further support the molecular dynamic simulation results wherein the hydroxyl groups are involved in hydrogen bonding with the polar headgroup of the lipid bilayers.

(f) ³¹P NMR : It is a useful technique for the study of the polymorphic phase behavior of hydrated phospholipids in excess water. Lipid phosphorus exhibits large chemical shift anisotropy. ³¹P NMR line shape is sensitive to different types of motions of lipid molecules. Dynamics of phospholipid bilayer system consists primarily of rapid rotation of the lipid molecules about their long axes and they have a characteristic broad spectrum with a high field peak and a low field shoulder³³. The ³¹P resonance line shape is determined by the chemical shift anisotropy (CSA) of the phosphate group coupled with the molecular motions near the head groups³⁴.

The effect of quercetin on the ³¹P NMR line shape was measured as a function of concentration and temperature. The chemical shift anisotropy (CSA) can be measured from the low and high field (the σ_{\parallel} and σ_{\perp} components) shoulders of the spectrum. On incorporation of varying concentrations of quercetin to the DPPC MLV's the ³¹P line shape is not affected i.e. the bilayer features remain intact. The lamellar phase persists at temperatures from 303 K to 333 K monitored at intervals of 10 K. The broadening of the lamellar ³¹P NMR signals of DPPC liposomes with increasing concentrations of quercetin thereby a decrease in the CSA parameter shows a decreased motional freedom/increased order of the phospholipid head group.

Conclusions :

Quercetin fluidizes the membrane and interacts with the hydrophilic head group of lipid. The nearby polyphenolic -OH groups present at positions 3', 4' of ring B and position 7 of ring A of quercetin are involved in binding with DPPC membranes. This is further supported by MD simulations whereby hydrogen bonds are formed between the polar head group and the hydroxyl groups of quercetin. These H-bonds pose a barrier to the entry of quercetin molecule deep into the hydrophobic part of the membranes. This may result in the erratic absorption of quercetin from the intestinal membranes. Removal or reduction in the number of these phenolic -OH groups may result in an increase in the permeability of quercetin in the membranes. Based on these results it may be suggested to modify the structure of quercetin with the hope to overcome the problem of permeability through the intestinal membrane.

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